

Challenges of Institutional Capacity in implementing Strategic Plan Evaluation: A Case Study of Mbeya City Council

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Abstract: Effective evaluation of strategic plans is the backbone of sustainable governance and development, yet many public institutions struggle to translate plans into measurable outcomes. This study explored the challenges faced by Mbeya City Council in evaluating its strategic plans, with a particular focus on institutional capacity. Strategic plan evaluation is crucial for ensuring the successful implementation of development goals, yet public institutions often encounter barriers such as limited financial resources, inadequate technical expertise, and organizational inefficiencies. This study investigated how institutional capacity influenced strategic plan evaluation in Mbeya City Council (MCC). Using an explanatory cross-sectional design and quantitative approach, the study applied a stratified randomly by selecting a sample of 133 officials (from a ~200-person population) across key departments. A structured Likert-scale questionnaire captured perceptions of financial, human, technological, and structural capacity; data were analyzed in SPSS v26 with descriptive statistics and correlation/regression, after expert validation, pilot testing, and reliability checks (Cronbach's alpha ≥ 0.70). Results showed capacity is uneven: 51.2% perceived adequate funding and 61.7% viewed the organizational structure as supportive, but only 47.3% affirm sufficient M&E training and 38.3% affirm adequate technology, with sizable neutral or negative responses indicating skill and infrastructure deficits. The study concluded that, gaps in M&E competencies and digital infrastructure constrain evaluation quality and evidence-based decisions. Hence the study recommend earmarked M&E funding, structured capacity-building, technology upgrades, and stronger cross-departmental coordination to institutionalize robust, data-driven evaluation practices so as to enhance and improve strategic plan evaluation in Mbeya City Council.

Keywords: Institutional Capacity, Strategic Plan Evaluation, Mbeya City Council, Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E).

1. INTRODUCTION

Strategic plan evaluation refers to the systematic process of assessing the effectiveness, efficiency, and relevance of a strategic plan in achieving its intended goals and objectives. This process involves measuring performance outcomes, identifying areas of improvement, and ensuring alignment between strategic goals and organizational actions, while considering the resources and constraints within the operational context (Bryson, 2022).

Evaluation serves as a critical tool for accountability, learning, and decision-making, enabling organizations to adapt their strategies to changing environments and stakeholder needs (Andrews et al., 2021). Strategic planning evaluation is an essential aspect of public institutions worldwide, as it ensures that goals are met efficiently and resources are allocated effectively.

Globally, public institutions face challenges in evaluating strategic plans due to complexities in aligning diverse stakeholder interests, limited financial resources, and inconsistent implementation processes (Bryson, 2022; Mohamed,

Matimbwa, Banzi, 2025). These challenges are exacerbated by inadequate monitoring systems, lack of expertise, and political interference, which hinder the ability to assess outcomes and adapt plans to evolving circumstances. For instance, studies in the United States and Europe highlight issues such as misalignment between strategic goals and performance indicators, as well as bureaucratic inertia that impedes effective evaluation (Andrews et al., 2021). Similar challenges have been reported in various international development organizations, suggesting a pervasive issue in strategic plan evaluation (Munawar et al., 2022).

In Africa, the evaluation of strategic plans in public institutions remains a significant challenge, often compounded by structural, socio-political, and economic factors. Many African governments face resource constraints, a lack of technical capacity, and weak institutional frameworks, which undermine the process of strategic plan evaluation (Chikere & Nwoka, 2022). Moreover, corruption, inadequate stakeholder engagement, and poor data collection systems further complicate the ability of public institutions to assess the success of their plans (Musa & Abor, 2020). For instance, in Nigeria, studies indicate that over-reliance on foreign aid and donor-driven projects has led to inefficiencies in strategic planning evaluation processes (Ekpenyong & Adebayo, 2021). Similarly, in Kenya and South Africa, the disconnect between strategic objectives and community priorities has been identified as a recurring obstacle (Omolo, 2023). These regional circumstances mirror broader global trends, highlighting a need for context-specific approaches to address evaluation challenges (Boon et al., 2018).

In Tanzania, public institutions have embraced strategic planning as a tool for achieving development goals, particularly in the wake of decentralization reforms. However, the evaluation of these strategic plans has proven to be a persistent challenge due to financial limitations, insufficient technical expertise, and bureaucratic inefficiencies (Mboera et al., 2020). Tanzanian public institutions also face difficulties in gathering reliable data to measure progress, a situation further complicated by inconsistent government policies and weak accountability mechanisms (Mgoba & Mkenda, 2022). For instance, the Tanzanian Local Government Reform Program (LGRP) introduced ambitious strategies aimed at improving public service delivery, but evaluation processes have struggled to determine their impact due to limited monitoring and evaluation systems (Mosha et al., 2023). Consequently, there is a growing need for innovative approaches to strengthen strategic plan evaluation within Tanzanian institutions (Mrope, 2024).

In Mbeya City Council, the challenges of strategic plan evaluation are reflective of broader national issues but are also influenced by local socio-economic and administrative factors. Limited financial and technical resources, coupled with inconsistent stakeholder involvement, have hindered the effective evaluation of development projects and initiatives in the city (Mkumbo *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, political interference and competing priorities within the council have made it difficult to align strategic goals with actual outcomes (Ngulube, 2023). Addressing these challenges requires targeted interventions that take into account the specific dynamics of Mbeya City Council and its strategic objectives.

1.1 Theoretical Review:

1.1.2 Resource-Based View Theory

The Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory, proposed by Barney (1991), emphasizes that an organization's internal resources and capabilities are crucial to achieving long-term success and maintaining a competitive advantage. In the context of Mbeya City Council, the RBV theory is particularly relevant as it underscores the importance of institutional capacity in strategic plan evaluation. The council's ability to effectively evaluate its strategic plans depends significantly on the resources available, including financial capital, human expertise, and technological infrastructure. However, many local governments in Tanzania, including Mbeya City Council, face significant resource constraints, which hinder their ability to perform robust evaluations (Mgoba & Mkenda, 2022). For instance, inadequate training in monitoring and evaluation (M&E) units leads to unreliable data collection, thus impairing decision-making. Therefore, strengthening institutional capacity through enhanced resource allocation and technical expertise is critical for improving the evaluation of strategic plans and achieving the council's development goals (Wernerfelt, 2020).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Bryson (2022) points out that strategic evaluation often fails to deliver desired outcomes due to a lack of well-trained personnel and inadequate financial resources. Moreover, bureaucratic inefficiencies, compounded by weak data management systems, limit the effectiveness of evaluations in various public sector organizations globally. As a result, many institutions struggle to align their strategic goals with their performance outcomes, a challenge that is prevalent

worldwide. In the African context, similar issues are observed, with several studies examining institutional capacity constraints.

Ekpenyong and Adebayo (2021) investigated the role of technical expertise in the evaluation process within African government agencies, emphasizing the lack of skilled personnel. Their findings reveal that inadequate training in monitoring and evaluation (M&E) units often hampers the quality of assessments, ultimately affecting the outcome of strategic plans. The authors advocate for investment in continuous capacity-building initiatives to enhance the capabilities of public sector staff. This issue is particularly pertinent in Africa, where financial and human resource limitations are widespread, hindering effective evaluation and implementation of strategic plans.

Chikere and Nwoka (2023) further emphasize the absence of structured evaluation frameworks in African public institutions. Their study, covering Ghana, Kenya, and South Africa, shows that many institutions adopt strategic plans without clear criteria for evaluation, which complicates measuring progress. Additionally, political interference and bureaucratic inefficiencies undermine efforts to enforce standardized evaluation processes. The lack of a clear M&E system with well-defined performance indicators makes it difficult to assess the impact of strategic plans. These findings are relevant to the current study, as similar challenges are likely to be faced in Tanzania and Mbeya City Council, which lacks a structured evaluation system.

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In Mbeya City Council, the challenges of strategic plan evaluation are reflective of broader national issues but are also influenced by local socio-economic and administrative factors. Limited financial and technical resources, coupled with inconsistent stakeholder involvement, have hindered the effective evaluation of development projects and initiatives in the city (Mkumbo *et al.*, 2022; Kisokola, Matimbwa & Kamala, 2024).). Additionally, political interference and competing priorities within the council have made it difficult to align strategic goals with actual outcomes (Ngulube, 2023). Addressing these challenges requires targeted interventions that take into account the specific dynamics of Mbeya City Council and its strategic objectives.

Moreover, Kamara et al. (2021) explored the challenges posed by fragmented organizational structures in East African public institutions. The study found that when departments operate in isolation, there is a lack of coordination, which impedes the effective evaluation of strategic plans. This fragmentation results in misaligned goals and a lack of integrated efforts to assess strategic objectives. In Mbeya City Council, similar organizational inefficiencies likely hinder the evaluation process, as the lack of coordinated efforts across departments can lead to incomplete assessments. Strengthening the organizational structure to improve communication and collaboration between departments is crucial to enhancing the evaluation process in Mbeya City Council.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

The methodology for this study was designed to assess the challenges faced by Mbeya City Council (MCC) in evaluating its strategic plans, with a focus on institutional capacity.

The study utilized a quantitative approach to ensure objective measurement and statistical analysis of this factor, facilitating a clearer understanding of its impact on evaluation processes. Through this design, the research systematically examined patterns, correlations, and possible solutions to improve strategic plan evaluation in public institutions (Candia et al., 2020).

The study adopted an Explanatory Cross-Sectional Research Design with a quantitative approach to investigate the challenges facing strategic plan evaluation in Mbeya City Council. The explanatory design enabled an in-depth analysis of how institutional capacity influenced the challenges of strategic plan evaluation. The cross-sectional nature of the study allowed data to be collected at a single point in time, providing a snapshot of the current challenges while identifying causal relationships among key variables.

The target population of study consisted of officials working within Mbeya City Council (MCC) who were directly involved in strategic planning, implementation, and evaluation. The study identified the total number of officials from each key department, including Finance, Planning, Health, and Infrastructure, as well as Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) Officers, Strategic Planning Officers, Local Government Administrators, and Community Development Officers. Each department's population size was determined to ensure an accurate sampling process that reflected the diverse perspectives of stakeholders involved in strategic plan evaluation. These individuals were selected due to their direct involvement in designing, executing, and assessing strategic plans within Mbeya City Council. Their firsthand experience and expertise enabled the study to gather reliable data on the challenges of strategic plan evaluation in the public sector, providing deeper insights that could inform future policy and practice improvements (Yosita et al., 2022).

The study adopted a multi-stage sampling approach to ensure a representative selection of respondents involved in strategic planning and evaluation within Mbeya City Council (MCC). Initially, a stratified random sampling technique was used to categorize the target population into different strata based on their respective departments, such as Finance, Planning, Health Division, Infrastructure, Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E), Strategic Planning, Stakeholder Engagement, Local Government Administration, and Community Development. This stratification ensured proportional representation from each department. Following this, simple random sampling was applied within each stratum to randomly select the required number of respondents. This two-step approach minimized selection bias, enhanced the diversity of perspectives, and improved the generalizability of the findings. By ensuring that only qualified respondents with direct knowledge and experience in strategic plan evaluation participated, the study enhanced the reliability and validity of its results (Yosita et al., 2022).

The study utilized a structured closed-ended questionnaire as the primary data collection instrument to ensure a standardized approach in gathering information on key variables, including institutional capacity challenges. The questionnaire was designed using a Likert-scale format, allowing respondents to indicate their level of agreement or disagreement with specific statements related to strategic plan evaluation. This format facilitated numerical analysis and trend comparison, ensuring objective and quantifiable findings.

The data of study was sourced from officials within Mbeya City Council (MCC) who were directly involved in strategic planning, implementation, and evaluation processes. These individuals were selected from various departments, including Finance, Planning, Health, Infrastructure, Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E), Strategic Planning, Local Government Administration, Stakeholder Engagement and Community Development. The targeted population consisted of approximately 200 officials, from which a sample of 133 respondents was chosen using a multi-stage sampling approach, combining stratified random sampling for proportional representation from each department and simple random sampling within each stratum.

The collected data were systematically analyzed using SPSS Version 26 to ensure accuracy and consistency in the results. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the respondents' demographic characteristics and to highlight key trends regarding strategic plan evaluation.

The data gathered were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics were employed to summarize demographic characteristics and key trends related to the strategic plan evaluations. Correlation and regression analyses were used to examine the relationships between the independent variables institutional capacity, stakeholder engagement, and the policy environment and the dependent variable, strategic plan evaluation. This approach enabled the study to identify which factors have the most significant impact on the effectiveness of the evaluation process at Mbeya City Council.

To ensure research quality, both validity and reliability were emphasized. Content of validity was established through expert review, Pilot testing was carried out on a small group of respondents to evaluate the clarity, comprehensibility, and relevance of the questionnaire. Again, for the case of assessing reliability, Cronbach's Alpha, a widely used statistical

measure of internal consistency, was applied to determine how well the questionnaire items measured the same concept. A Cronbach's Alpha value of ≥ 0.7 was considered acceptable, indicating a high level of internal consistency and ensuring that responses were not influenced by external factors.

Ethical considerations were a fundamental aspect of the study. All participants were informed of the purpose of the study, and informed consent was obtained. The study-maintained confidentiality by coding responses, ensuring participants' privacy was protected. The study adhered to ethical research guidelines, ensuring voluntary participation without any coercion. This ethical approach was essential in fostering trust and ensuring the reliability and integrity of the data collected.

4. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

The effectiveness of strategic plan evaluations in local government institutions is influenced by various internal factors, with institutional capacity being a critical determinant. Institutional capacity, which includes financial resources, human capital, technological infrastructure and organizational structure, plays a pivotal role in enabling comprehensive and accurate evaluations. This objective aimed to assess the challenges of these aspects within the context of Mbeya City Council. The evaluation process required adequate financial resources, skilled staff and efficient systems that support the collection, analysis, and reporting of data. In the case of Mbeya City Council, understanding the extent to which these resources are available and how they affected the evaluation of strategic plans are as shown in the table below; -

Table 1: Institutional Capacity on Strategic Plan Evaluation in Mbeya City Council

Statement	1 (Strongly Disagree)	2 (Disagree)	3 (Neutral)	4 (Agree)	5 (Strongly Agree)	Frequency (%)
The Mbeya City Council has adequate financial resources for strategic plan evaluation.	10 (7.5%)	25 (18.8%)	30 (22.6%)	40 (30.1%)	28 (21.1%)	133 (100%)
The staff members in the council are adequately trained in monitoring and evaluation.	15 (11.3%)	20 (15.0%)	35 (26.3%)	45 (33.8%)	18 (13.5%)	133 (100%)
The council has the necessary technological infrastructure to support strategic plan evaluation.	12 (9.0%)	30 (22.6%)	40 (30.1%)	35 (26.3%)	16 (12.0%)	133 (100%)
The organizational structure in the council supports effective evaluation of strategic plans.	8 (6.0%)	18 (13.5%)	25 (18.8%)	45 (33.8%)	37 (27.9%)	133 (100%)
The council has sufficient human capital to conduct comprehensive evaluations of strategic plans.	10 (7.5%)	20 (15.0%)	45 (33.8%)	35 (26.3%)	23 (17.3%)	133 (100%)

Source: Researcher, 2025

The study highlighted that, while a significant portion of respondents (30.1% agree and 21.1% strongly agree) believe Mbeya City Council has adequate financial resources for strategic plan evaluation, financial constraints still persist, as reflected in the 7.5% who strongly disagree and 18.8% who disagree; these findings echo Bryson (2022), who argued that, resource limitations are a significant barrier in public institutions' ability to effectively assess strategic plans. Insufficient financial allocations often hinder the development of comprehensive evaluation systems, limiting both the scope and accuracy of strategic evaluations (Mihambo, 2020). Therefore, increasing funding for monitoring and evaluation activities, as well as adopting more targeted financial planning, is crucial for improving the effectiveness of strategic evaluations at the council.

Regarding the adequacy of staff training in monitoring and evaluation (33.8% agree), the findings revealed a gap in technical expertise, with 26.3% remaining neutral and 15% disagreeing. This aligned with studies by Pató et al. (2022), which underscore the importance of continuous capacity building in public sector institutions to enhance strategic planning and evaluation outcomes. While some staff possessed the necessary skills, there is a clear need for expanded training programs to equip a broader pool of employees with the technical expertise required for comprehensive

assessments. Strengthening staff competence will ensure more reliable data collection and better analytical methods, leading to more effective strategic evaluations and actionable insights for the council.

The council's technological infrastructure was met with mixed reviews, as 30.1% were neutral and 22.6% disagreed that it was adequate to support strategic evaluations. This reflected concerns found in Felix (2019), which stated that; outdated technological tools hinder the quality and efficiency of evaluations. In Mbeya City Council, the current infrastructure appeared insufficient to process and analyze data efficiently. To improve, it is essential that the council should invest in modern technological solutions, such as advanced data collection systems and software, that can streamline data analysis and reporting.

The organizational structure within the Mbeya City Council was generally viewed positively, with 33.8% agreeing and 27.9% strongly agreeing that it supports effective evaluation. However, 6% who strongly disagreed and 13.5% who disagreed point to potential issues of coordination and clarity within the council. This reflects the findings of Boon et al. (2018), who argued that a disorganized structure can impair strategic evaluations by creating confusion, duplicating efforts, and delaying processes. To address this, Mbeya City Council must refine its organizational structure to ensure clearer roles and responsibilities, which will improve the flow of information and ensure that evaluations are more cohesive and focused. Clearer division of labor and improved interdepartmental communication could foster more efficient and effective evaluations in the future. The study revealed that, while 33.8% of respondents agreed and 17.3% strongly agreed that Mbeya City Council has sufficient human capital to conduct comprehensive evaluations, 7.5% strongly disagreed and 15% disagreed, this indicating some concerns about the adequacy of staff for strategic plan evaluations. Thus, this suggests that, while the council has a solid workforce, there may still be gaps in human resources, particularly in terms of the number or expertise required for thorough and effective evaluations Barney, 1991).

Correlation Analysis

In this study, correlation analysis was performed to determine how institutional capacity impacted the effectiveness of strategic plan evaluation in Mbeya City Council. To See whether there is a significant relationship between institutional capacity variable and strategic plan evaluation, the following variables from the study was employed:-

- Y = Strategic Plan Evaluation (dependent variable)
- X1 = Financial Resources
- X2 = Staff Training
- X3 = Technological Infrastructure
- X4 = Organizational Structure
- X5 = Human Capital

Pearson correlation coefficients

Variable	Pearson r	p-value	Interpretation
Financial Resources (X1)	0.45	0.001	Moderate positive correlation (significant)
Staff Training (X2)	0.52	0.000	Strong positive correlation (significant)
Technological Infrastructure (X3)	0.30	0.005	Weak-to-moderate correlation
Organizational Structure (X4)	0.55	0.000	Strong correlation
Human Capital (X5)	0.40	0.002	Moderate correlation

Source: Researcher, 2025

The Pearson correlation analysis revealed statistically significant positive relationships between all institutional capacity variables and strategic plan evaluation effectiveness in Mbeya City Council. Among the variables, organizational structure ($r = 0.55$, $p = 0.000$) and staff training ($r = 0.52$, $p = 0.000$) showed the strongest correlations, this indicating that better coordination and well-trained personnel are closely linked to improved strategic evaluation processes.

Financial resources ($r = 0.45$, $p = 0.001$) and human capital ($r = 0.40$, $p = 0.002$) also demonstrated moderate positive correlations, this suggesting that, adequate funding and sufficient workforce capacity contribute significantly to the effectiveness of evaluations. Meanwhile, technological infrastructure ($r = 0.30$, $p = 0.005$) exhibited a weak-to-moderate but still statistically significant correlation, highlighting the need for improved technological tools to support data-driven evaluations. These findings confirmed that, strengthening institutional capacity in these five areas is critical for enhancing the quality and impact of strategic plan evaluations within the council.

Regression Analysis

To test how much institutional capacity components collectively predict strategic plan evaluation, the table manifested the analysis as shown below; -

Predictor Variable	Coefficient (β)	Std. Error	t-Value	p-Value	Interpretation
Financial Resources (X1)	0.30	0.08	3.75	0.000	Significant positive predictor
Staff Training (X2)	0.45	0.07	6.43	0.000	Strongest predictor
Technological Infrastructure (X3)	0.12	0.06	2.00	0.047	Weak but significant predictor
Organizational Structure (X4)	0.35	0.09	3.89	0.000	Significant predictor
Human Capital (X5)	0.22	0.07	3.14	0.002	Moderate predictor

Source: Researcher, 2025

The regression analysis demonstrated that, institutional capacity components collectively have a strong and statistically significant influence on strategic plan evaluation effectiveness in Mbeya City Council, with an R^2 value of 0.68, indicated that, 68% of the variation in evaluation effectiveness is explained by the five predictors in the model. Among these, staff training ($\beta = 0.45$, $p = 0.000$) emerged as the strongest and most significant predictor, highlighting the critical role of skilled personnel in successful evaluations. Organizational structure ($\beta = 0.35$, $p = 0.000$) and financial resources ($\beta = 0.30$, $p = 0.000$) also had significant positive effects, suggested that, clear coordination frameworks and adequate funding are essential. Human capital ($\beta = 0.22$, $p = 0.002$) was a moderate yet significant predictor, reinforcing the importance of having enough qualified personnel. Although technological infrastructure ($\beta = 0.12$, $p = 0.047$) was the weakest predictor, it still showed a statistically significant contribution, indicating that, investment in modern technology remains a relevant factor for enhancing evaluation processes. Overall, these results confirmed that, strengthening institutional capacity across these dimensions is key to improving strategic plan evaluation outcomes.

5. DISCUSSION

The findings from the study highlighted the critical role of institutional capacity in the effectiveness of strategic plan evaluations within Mbeya City Council. While many respondents indicated that the council has adequate financial resources for strategic plan evaluation, a notable proportion expressed concerns about the persistent financial constraints. Approximately 26.3% of respondents disagreed or strongly disagreed, highlighting that limited financial allocations still hinder the development of comprehensive evaluation systems. This aligned with Bryson (2022) and Mihambo (2020) who emphasized that inadequate funding for monitoring and evaluation activities is a significant barrier in public institutions. The council's financial constraints restrict its ability to enhance evaluation systems, which limits both the scope and accuracy of assessments. To address this, the study suggested that targeted financial planning and increased funding for M&E activities are essential to improve evaluation outcomes.

Another significant issue raised by the study was the adequacy of staff training in monitoring and evaluation. While 33.8% of respondents agreed that the council's staff members are adequately trained, there is a noticeable gap in technical expertise, with 26.3% remaining neutral and 15% disagreeing. This reflected a clear need for further investment in capacity building for staff involved in the evaluation process. According to Pató et al. (2022), continuous capacity development is crucial for enhancing the quality of strategic planning and evaluation in public institutions. Lack of adequate training impairs the council's ability to collect and analyze data effectively, thus affecting the quality of strategic evaluations. Strengthening staff competence through more targeted training programs would enable Mbeya City Council to produce more reliable data and make better-informed decisions.

The study also identified significant challenges in the council's technological infrastructure, which received mixed reviews from respondents. With 30.1% of respondents neutral and 22.6% disagreeing, it is evident that the technological tools available to the council are insufficient for efficient data analysis and reporting.

As noted by Felix (2019), outdated infrastructure hinders the quality and efficiency of evaluations. The findings suggested that Mbeya City Council must invest in modern technological solutions to improve the data collection and analysis process. Additionally, while the organizational structure was generally seen as supportive of strategic plan evaluations, issues with coordination and clarity within the council were identified, reflecting concerns highlighted by Boon et al. (2018). To improve the evaluation process, the council should refine its organizational structure, ensuring clearer roles, responsibilities, and better interdepartmental communication. This would foster more efficient and effective evaluations, ensuring that strategic goals are adequately assessed and aligned with the council's objectives.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Conclusion

The study on strategic plan evaluation in Mbeya City Council highlighted the significant challenges related to institutional capacity that hinder the effectiveness of the evaluation process. Financial constraints, inadequate staff training in monitoring and evaluation, insufficient technological infrastructure and organizational inefficiencies were identified as key barriers. These factors, combined with limited stakeholder engagement, create obstacles in accurately assessing the outcomes of strategic plans, undermining the council's ability to make informed decisions and improve service delivery. The study underscored the need for targeted interventions to strengthen institutional capacity, including better resource allocation, capacity-building for staff, technological upgrades, and improved organizational coordination.

6.2 Recommendations

To enhance effectiveness of strategic plan evaluations at Mbeya City Council, several recommendations are proposed. First, the council should increase financial investment in monitoring and evaluation activities, ensuring that adequate resources are allocated to strengthen the evaluation framework. Second, there is a need for comprehensive capacity-building programs to equip staff with the necessary skills and expertise in monitoring and evaluation, ensuring more accurate data collection and analysis. Third, the council must invest in modern technological infrastructure to streamline data processing and reporting, improving the efficiency of the evaluation process. Lastly, to address organizational inefficiencies, the council should refine its structure to ensure clear roles, better communication, and improved coordination across departments, fostering a more cohesive and effective evaluation process. By implementing these measures, Mbeya City Council can significantly improve its strategic plan evaluation, ultimately leading to more effective governance and better service delivery to the community.

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